

FORMULATION OPTIMIZATION AND IN VITRO EVALUATION OF SPANLASTICS LOADED WITH ACCELOFENAC

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Abstract

The goal of this research was to explore the potential of a novel nanovesicular system known as Spanlastics and conventional formulation (Ointment) for the transdermal conveyance of Aceclofenac (ACF) to alleviate its adverse effects on the gastrointestinal tract when administered orally. ACF-loaded spanlastics were formulated through the ethanol injection method to investigate the impact of formulation variables on drug content (%DC), Entrapment efficiency (%EE), particle size (PS), and the percentage of drug released after 5 hours through both cellulose and Egg membranes, in comparison to the Ointment. The optimized composition, consisting of Span 60 as non-ionic surfactant and Tween 80 as an edge activator at a 1:1 ratio, demonstrated the highest %EE ($77.85 \pm 0.98\%$), a PS of 268.8nm, and a Q5h of $74.81 \pm 2.05\%$. Morphological features were examined using Optical Microscopy and TEM. The in-vitro release study of ACF-loaded spanlastic gel and conventional ointment through cellulose and egg membranes was assessed. The results of the in-vitro release study revealed that the spanlastic gel showcased both sustained and prolonged effects. In conclusion, a gel based on spanlastics may represent a promising approach for enhancing the transdermal delivery of aceclofenac, offering both extended and intensified efficacy in pain management.

Keywords - Spanlastics, Novel nanocarrier, Spanlastic gel, Ethanol injection method

I. Introduction

The administration of numerous medications, including nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs), via oral routes is frequently restricted due to the potential for severe adverse effects on the gastrointestinal system. Aceclofenac (ACF), belonging to the NSAID class, is utilized for pain, inflammation, and stiffness management associated with osteoarthritis and rheumatoid arthritis. The use of ACF orally is constrained due to gastrointestinal issues like irritation, ulceration, and gastric bleeding (Sweetman SC, 2011). Additionally, it exhibits a short elimination half-life (4-4.3 h), necessitating frequent doses for sustained anti-inflammatory effects (Mankala SK, 2011). Despite the oral route is frequently employed for drug administration due to its convenience, it is burdened with limitations such as inadequate bioavailability and rapid fluctuations in blood levels. To overcome these limitations and improve the effectiveness and safety of treatment, the development of novel drug delivery systems becomes imperative. Therefore, the topical application of aceclofenac holds promise in circumventing oral side effects and precisely targeting the drug to inflamed skin, ultimately enhancing patient compliance (Idrees MA, 2011).

Topical drug application offers advantages such as bypassing hepatic first-pass metabolism, improving patient compliance and accessibility, providing rapid dosing termination, sustaining therapeutic drug levels, potential self-administration, non-invasiveness, avoidance of food interactions, and reduced doses compared to oral and intravenous routes. However, topical delivery faces challenges like poor skin permeability, unpredictable drug release, and skin irritation. Overcoming these challenges can be achieved through the development of transdermal drug delivery systems (TDDS) employing nano-sized drug carriers, which provide enhanced localization to the target site and sustained drug release while minimizing adverse reactions.

Spanlastics, a type of nano-drug delivery carrier, is composed of non-ionic surfactants and edge activators, which give their structure high elasticity and deformability. The use of an edge activator allows spanlastic vesicles to become ultra-flexible and deformable, making them a sophisticated and more advantageous than niosomes.

These pliable nanovesicles exhibit enhanced capability not only to surmount the stratum corneum barrier but also in adeptly permeating deep subcutaneous target tissues by squeezing through pores much smaller than their own size while maintaining their structural integrity (Cevc G, 2008). Their flexibility allows them to traverse channels less than one-tenth of their diameter (Kumar GP, 2011); thus, drug-loaded spanlastics can penetrate the skin spontaneously, regardless of concentration (Cevc G, 2008).

The flexibility of spanlastics can be attributed to edge activators (EAs), which destabilize the vesicles, fluidize the vesicular bilayer by reducing interfacial tension, and promote improved drug penetration (Kakkar S, 2011). Consequently, spanlastics employ a distinctive mechanism of drug transport, demonstrating heightened efficiency in delivering both low and high molecular weight drugs to the skin in terms of quantity and depth (Choi MJ, 2005). Furthermore, they offer prolonged action and superior biological activity compared to traditional niosomes (Kumar GP, 2011).

Spanlastics are nanovesicles, that enclose the drug within the core cavity of a bilayer structure. It can be employed to transport amphiphilic drugs i.e., both hydrophilic and lipophilic drugs. So, aceclofenac (ACF) being lipophilic in nature can be delivered using this carrier to enhance its permeability across skin, increase its solubility and to give a sustained release. Considering the better stability, affordability, and elasticity than liposomes and niosomes, spanlastics play a vital role in overcoming the complications linked with the conventional dose form including first pass metabolism, incompatibility with medication excipients, and patient noncompliance. Spanlastics appears to be a widely desired drug delivery technology.

The aim of this research was to enhance the transdermal administration of aceclofenac through the development of spanlastics loaded with ACF. This strategy aimed to achieve superior skin permeation and controlled release, potentially augmenting the therapeutic effectiveness of the drug while mitigating its adverse effects. Employing the ethanol injection method, ACF-loaded spanlastics were fabricated, and diverse formulation variables were investigated to understand their influence on vesicle characteristics, including entrapment efficiency (%EE), vesicle size, and in vitro drug release. Consequently, an evaluation and comparison were conducted between ACF-loaded spanlastic gel and conventional formulations.

II. Materials and Methods

Aceclofenac was a gift sample and all other chemicals used were of analytical grade.

2.1 Preparation of drug loaded Spanlastics (ACF-SL)

Aceclofenac spanlastics were prepared by ethanol injection method (Kakkar S. 2011). Initially, the drug was dissolved in 2mL ethanol and weighed quantity of Span 60 (non-ionic surfactant). Meanwhile, the aqueous phase, consisting of an edge activator (Tween 80), was stirred continuously and maintained at a temperature of 70°C to 80°C in a separate beaker. Then, the drug solution was slowly injected into the edge activator's aqueous dispersion at 70°C while stirring at 600-700 rpm. The resulting mixture was stirred for an additional 30 minutes to allow ethanol to evaporate and after that subjected to sonication for 2 minutes. The final formulation was stored appropriately at 4°C until further evaluations. By varying the drug concentration, non-ionic surfactant and edge activator's ratio; the different composition of ACF-SL formulations is shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Formulation table of spanlastics (SL)

S. No.	Formulation Code	Non-ionic surfactant: Edge Activator	Drug (mg/ml)	Span 60 (mg/ml)	Tween 80 (mg/ml)
1	M1	8:2	10	160	40
2	M2	1:1	10	100	100
3	M3	9:1	10	180	20
4	M4	7:3	10	140	60
5	M5	3:2	10	120	80
6	M6	8:2	5	160	40
7	M7	1:1	5	100	100
8	M8	9:1	5	180	20

9	M9	7:3	5	140	60
10	M10	3:2	5	120	80

2.2 Preparation of drug loaded Ointments

Different ointment bases loaded with ACF were prepared by fusion method followed by congealing. Different bases chosen for ointment base were Hydrophilic petrolatum (A) Lanolin base (B), Hydrophilic base (C), Macrogol base (D), Oleaginous base (E), Simple ointment base (F). Composition of different bases are listed in Table 2.

Table 2: Formulation table of ointments

Ointment A	Qty /1000g	Ointment B	Qty /100g
Acceclofenac	15g	Acceclofenac	1.5%
Cholesterol	30g	Lanolin	35%
Stearyl alcohol	30g	Mineral Oil	30%
White wax	80g	Purified water	33.5%
White petrolatum	845g		
Ointment C	Qty /1000g	Ointment D	Qty /100g
Acceclofenac	15%	Acceclofenac	1.5%
Methyl paraben	0.25%	PEG 4000	40%
Propyl paraben	0.15%	PEG 300	58.5%
SLS	10%		
Propylene glycol	120%		
Stearyl alcohol	250%		
White petrolatum	250%		
Purified water	355%		
Ointment E	Qty /100g	Ointment F	Qty /100g
Acceclofenac	1.5%	Acceclofenac	1.5%
Hard paraffin	3%	Hard paraffin	5%
White soft paraffin	83.5%	White soft paraffin	83.5%
White beeswax	2%	Lanolin (wool fat)	5%
Cetostearyl alcohol	5%	Cetostearyl alcohol	5%
Propylene glycol	5%		

2.3 Preparation of ACF-loaded-SL gel (ACF-SL-GEL)

To prepare the Carbopol gel (1.5% w/w), Carbopol was gradually added to water and stirred overnight. The mixture was then allowed to stand for 24 hours to eliminate trapped air. Afterward, the pH was adjusted using triethylamine to achieve the desired consistency and pH. The optimized spanlastics (SL) formulation was then dispersed into the Carbopol base to obtain ACF-loaded SL gel.

2.4 Characterization of prepared vesicles

Entrapment Efficiency (EE%)

The aqueous ACF-loaded spanlastics dispersion is dialyzed against methanol by placing 1mL of ACF-SL dispersion in dialysis membrane-70 which was previously soaked in 50% methanol. The dialysis bag was then transferred to 50mL of methanol and stirred using magnetic stirrer. The test was conducted in triplicate. Samples were collected after 45 minutes and diluted with methanol to determine the absorbance at 275nm. The % EE of the drug was determined using the following equation:

$$EE\% = \frac{\text{Total drug content} - \text{unentrapped drug}}{\text{Theoretical drug content}} \times 100$$

Particle size, PDI and Zeta Potential (ZP)

The vesicles size was determined by dynamic light scattering method (DLS), using a computerized inspection system (Anton Paar Zetasizer). The spanlastics dispersion was diluted 100 times with distilled water, vortexed for 15 minutes and then subjected to particle analyzer. The readings were then taken at 25°C. The Z-average

value determined by DLS corresponds to the average hydrodynamic diameter of the spanlastics under examination (Kumar N. et al., 2020). PDI is used to describe the degree of non-uniformity of a size distribution of particles.

Zeta potential (ZP) of the prepared formulations was computed following suitable dilution with deionized water, The average ZP of three replicates was assessed at a temperature of 25°C (Haider MJ and Mehdi MS, 2014).

Optical Microscopy

The optimized drug loaded spanlastics dispersion was appropriately diluted (1:100) with double distilled water and subsequently applied onto a glass slide. The glass slide was then examined under an optical microscope at 40x and 100x magnification.

Transmission electron microscopy (TEM)

Transmission electron microscopy was used to visualise vesicles shape and surface morphology. Sample was prepared by diluting final dispersion to 100 times with double distilled water. The sample was dried on a microscopic carbon covered grid and the excess fluid was collected with filter paper. Then the sample was quickly frozen at liquid nitrogen, followed by freeze dried at -55°C (Rukari T and Babita A, 2013).

2.5 Characterization of ACF loaded ointments and gel

Measurement of pH

0.5 g ACF loaded ointments and gel was dispersed in 50 ml double distilled water. After 2h, the electrode was dipped in the prepared dispersion and measurements were recorded in triplicate from digital pH meter and average value were calculated (Gupta N et al., 2015).

Rheological study

Rheological behaviour was measured by a modular compact rheometer (Anton Paar Pvt Ltd., Ostifildern, Germany) at 25°C. The flow property measurements of the ointemnts and gel were carried out by step stress test in which the shear stress was increased from 100 to 400 Pa with equilibration time of 6 s at each point. Results were interpreted by plotting between shear stress vs shear rate and shear rate vs viscosity (Shah KA et al., 2007).

Spreadability

The Spreadability of the ACF-loaded gel and ointments were evaluated by parallel plate method as reported. The study was performed by taking 500 mg each of the formulations and placing it on the glass plate at centre, another glass plate of known weights was concentrically placed above it. The formulations were pressed with known weights at an interval of 30s between each weight. Spreadability of the formulations was measured by measuring the diameter of the formulation in two perpendicular directions (Marchiori ML et al., 2010).

The Spreadability factor was calculated using the following equation:

$$S_f = \frac{A}{W}$$

Where S_f ($\text{cm}^2 \cdot \text{g}^{-1}$) is the spreadability factor, defined as the ratio of the maximum spread area (A) in cm^2 after the addition of the sequence of weights and the total weights and total weight added (W) in gm. Spreadability profile was obtained by plotting the spreading area on y-axis Where and weights added on x-axis.

***In-vitro* drug release studies**

The cellulose dialysis membrane-70, measuring approximately 28.36mm flat width, 17.5mm diameter 2×2 cm (HiMedia Laboratories Pvt Ltd, Mumbai, India). It was soaked in phosphate buffer saline pH 7.4 overnight to activate the membrane before being utilised on the diffusion cell for drug release. The drug release experiment was conducted in an open-ended cylinder diffusion cell. The diffusion cell apparatus consists of a glass tube with an inner diameter of 2.5 cm, open at both ends. One end of the tube tied with dialysis membrane which serves as a donor compartment. The formulation was administered to the dialysis membrane via the donor compartment and placed in a beaker called reservoir compartment (Shreedevi HM et al., 2016). The reservoir compartment was filled with 30 mL of pH 7.4 phosphate buffer saline (PBS) and methanol with a ratio of 2:1. The experiment lasted 5 hours and was conducted at $37 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$ and 100 rpm. At predetermined intervals (15, 30, 60, 120, 180, 240 and 300 minutes) samples were collected from the reservoir compartment and absorbance was measured spectrophotometrically at 272nm after appropriate dilution. Immediately after sample collection, each time the reservoir compartment was filled with the same amount of solvent to maintain the sink conditions.

In-vitro release study via egg membrane

In-vitro drug release study was performed on an open-ended cylinder diffusion cell. 0.5g of each formulation, that is, ointments and gel was placed on one side of the egg shell membrane which acts as a barrier membrane because the egg shell membrane resembles human stratum corneum as it consists mainly of keratin (Saleem MN and Idris M et al.,2016). Egg membrane was previously extracted by soaking whole egg in 0.1N HCl solution followed by manual removal of the shell, then washed with distilled water thrice. It can be stored in distilled water for 1 week from 4°- 8°C (Shah V et., 2010; Haigh JM and Smith EW, 1994).

The donar compartment was then placed in a beaker (receiver compartment) containing 30 mL of PBS pH 7.4 and methanol in 2:1 ratio, which was stirred at 200 rpm and maintained at temperature $37 \pm 0.5^{\circ}\text{C}$. At predetermined intervals (15, 30, 60, 120, 180, 240 and 300 minutes) samples were collected from the reservoir compartment and absorbance was measured spectrophotometrically at 272 nm after suitable dilution. The reservoir compartment was filled with the same amount of solvent withdrawn each time to maintain the sink conditions.

III. Results and Discussion

3.1 Characterization of prepared vesicles

Particle size and Polydispersity Index (PDI)

The particle size and polydispersity index (PDI) of the formulated spanlastics are given in Table 3. Results indicated that the particles of the M2 dispersion was in the nanoscale size range (268.8nm) with low PDI of 0.328 as shown in Fig. 1 when compared to the other formulations.

Table 3: Observation of ACF loaded spanlastics (ACF-SL)

Formulation code	%EE \pm SD	Size (nm)	PDI	Zeta (mV)	Observations
M1	67.75 \pm 1.68	105.8	0.554	-8.39	PDI was high
M2	77.85 \pm 0.98	268.8	0.328	-11.4	Stability was good with less PDI and creamy appearance
M3	66.81 \pm 1.29	-	-	-	Percent entrapment efficiency was less as compared to other ratios
M4	72.33 \pm 0.78	123.7	0.484	-9.58	Stability was good but PDI showed two peaks
M5	70.80 \pm 0.54	374.3	0.632	-	Appearance was normal but PDI was high
M6	64.54 \pm 0.83	147.8	0.471	-13.2	Maybe sonication caused aggregation, on storage complete separation.
M7	73.07 \pm 1.84	367.1	0.520	-11.2	Stability was good but PDI showed two peaks
M8	63.63 \pm 0.49	-	-	-	Percent entrapment efficiency was less as compared to other ratios
M9	71.93 \pm 1.24	81.67	0.391	-5.80	Phase separation on storage
M10	68.80 \pm 0.66	-	-	-	Complete separation after 2 days

Figure 1: Particle size and PDI of ACF-loaded spanlastic

Zeta Potential (ZP)

Zeta potential of formulation was found to be between -5.80 to -13.2. It was concluded from the results that M2 dispersion having the value of -11.4 mV (Fig. 2) and represents a greater stability amongst all other formulations. Observations are explained in Table 3.

Figure 2: Zeta potential of ACF-loaded spanlastic dispersion

Percent Entrapment Efficiency (EE)

The analysis of the entrapment efficiency (% EE) of the formulated spanlastics was performed to determine the amount of ACF contained within the nanovesicles, and the findings are outlined in Table 3. The value of % EE of M1-M10 was found to be between $63.63 \pm 0.49\%$ - $77.85 \pm 0.98\%$. M2 has the highest %EE.

Optical Microscopy

Optical microscopy of M2 dispersion was determined at 40x [Fig. 3 (a)] and 100x [Fig. 3 (b)] magnification and the visual inspection of the particles verified that they exhibited bilamellar and multi-lamellar vesicle structures, with small and uniformly round shapes, and no signs of aggregation were observed as given in Fig. 3.

Figure 3: Optical photomicrographs of M2 formulation (a) 40x magnification (b) 100x magnification

Transmission electron microscopy (TEM)

Visual characterization of the vesicles was examined by transmission electron microscopy. Fig. 4, shows TEM images of optimized spanlastic dispersion indicating spherical shape and nano size, the surface morphology of particles was found to be smooth.

Figure 4: TEM images of optimized spanlastics at 500nm and 200nm

3.2 Characterization of Ointments and ACF-SL gel

Determination of pH

The pH of ACF-SL gel and ointments were measured in triplicate and pH determination of formulations was found to be in the range of 4.75-6.84 as depicted in Table 4. The pH of ACF-SL gel and D ointment was found to be 6.72 and 6.84 respectively, which is near to neutral pH. Thus, considered desirable to avoid the skin irritation upon application.

Table 4: TDC and pH value of different formulations:

Formulation code	pH (n=3)	Spread ability factor (cm ² g ⁻¹)
A	5.69	0.01
B	5.53	0.058

C	4.98	0.012
D	6.72	0.03
E	4.75	0.016
F	6.26	0.015
ACF-SL gel	6.84	0.087

Spreadability

The spreading area of gel was found to be higher 0.087 cm² g⁻¹ as compared to the ointments which means gel can be applied to skin with less force of application. The spreadability factor for gel and ointments are shown in Table 4. This concludes that ACF-SL gel has better spreadability as compared to ointments.

Rheological study

From the plots, it is clear that the D ointment (Fig. 5; i) and ACF loaded SL gel (Fig. 5; ii) showed pseudoplastic behaviour which indicates that the formulation show resistance, decreases when applied under medium to high shear rate which is desirable for topical formulation. This finding indicates that the ACF-SL gel is less viscous, leading to reduced retention on the skin. This decrease in retention time on the skin is an essential factor for an effective transdermal formulation.

Figure 5: Shear rate (γ) vs. shear stress (τ) and viscosity (η) i) D Ointment ii) ACF-SL gel

In-vitro drug release profile

It was clearly seen that D ointment showed the highest release profile amongst all the ointments; could be because of the solubility enhancing property of PEG's and thus was selected for further studies. Whereas, when compared with nano-formulation, M2 dispersion and ACF-SL gel showed higher drug release because of its nano structured carrier and ethanol used, as ethanol enhances drug permeation through the skin by either disrupting the skin barrier structure or increasing drug solubility in the stratum corneum, also ethanol reduces the viscosity of Carbopol gel to improve drug diffusion and permeation through membrane. Thus, the ACF-SL gel was selected for further studies because of its ease of application. This release profile is further assessed by in-vitro drug release via egg shell membrane. Fig. 6 portrays the comparative % drug release profile curve vs time for ACF ointments namely, A,B,C,D,E,F, M2 dispersion and ACF-SL gel.

Figure 6: In-vitro drug release profile of various formulations

In-vitro drug release study via egg shell membrane

The in-vitro drug release study using an egg shell membrane was conducted on the selected batch of ointment "D" and ACF-SL gel for 5h. The findings clearly revealed that ACF-SL gel (74.81 ± 2.05) exhibited higher drug permeation through the egg membrane compared to D ointment (66.76 ± 2.73). Moreover, the initial burst release obtained from ACF-SL gel might be due to the presence of untrapped drug in the formulation. However, it was observed that the drug release was ultimately reduced when compared to the results obtained from drug release via a cellulose dialysis membrane. This reduction in drug release could potentially be attributed to the barrier properties inherent by the egg membrane, which mimic the characteristics of the dermis layer in human skin. Fig. 7, portrays the comparative % drug release profile curve vs time for ACF loaded ointment D and ACF-SL gel.

Figure7: In-vitro drug release profile of ointment and gel via egg membrane

IV. Conclusion

According to the research findings, SLs could enhance and sustain the transdermal delivery of ACF, showing promise as a vesicular system. The optimized formulation displayed minimal particle size, appropriate zeta potential, spherical morphology and relatively high drug entrapment efficiency. ACF release from the system was sustained unlike conventional ointments. Incorporating the optimized M2 dispersion into gel base provided more enhanced effect and drug release. This sustained action of the ACF through the transdermal gel may provide prolonged pain relief, possibly replacing oral therapy and avoiding gastrointestinal side effects. The drug delivery system developed may target the inflamed tissue and avoid the accumulation of drugs in other tissues, thereby minimizing the side effects of drugs. In a nutshell, ACF-loaded nano-elastic spanlastics was prepared in a cost-effective manner and had better drug release than conventional formulation. Thus, diverse studies that we undertook and investigate and diligent efforts within the framework of the plan led us to accomplish the final goal of the optimized delivery of ACF in a nano-carrier based novel drug delivery system that can possibly alleviate.

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References:

- [1] Sweetman SC, editor. Martindale: the complete drug reference. 37th ed. London: Pharmaceutical Press; 2011.
- [2] Mankala, S. K., Korla, A. C., & Gade, S. (2011). Development and evaluation of aceclofenac-loaded mucoadhesive microcapsules. *Journal of advanced pharmaceutical technology & research*, 2(4), 245–254. <https://doi.org/10.4103/2231-4040.90881>.
- [3] Idrees MA, Rahman NU, Ahmad S, Ali MY, Ahmad I. Enhance transdermal delivery of flurbiprofen via microemulsions: effects of different types of surfactants and cosurfactants. *J DARU*. 2011;19(6):433–9.
- [4] Cevc G, Mazgareanu S, Rother M. Preclinical characterisation of NSAIDs in ultradeformable carriers or conventional topical gels. *Int J Pharm*. 2008;360:29–39.
- [5] Kakkar S, Kaur IP. Spanlastics — A novel nanovesicular carrier system for ocular delivery. *Int J Pharm*. 2011;413:202-210.
- [6] Kumar GP, Rajeshwarrao P. Nonionic surfactant vesicular systems for effective drug delivery—an overview. *Acta Pharm Sin B*. 2011;1(4):208–19.
- [7] Choi MJ, Maibach HI. Elastic vesicles as topical/transdermal drug delivery systems. *Int J Cosmetic Science*. 2005;27:211–21.
- [8] Kumar N, Dubey A, Mishra A, Tiwari P. Ethosomes: A Novel Approach in Transdermal Drug Delivery System. *International Journal of Pharmacy & Life Sciences*. 2020 May1;11(5).
- [9] Haider MJ, Mehdi MS. Study of morphology and zeta potential analyzer for the silver nanoparticles. *Int J Sci Eng Res*. 2014;5(7):1-7.
- [10] Rukari T and Babita A. Review article Transmission Electron Microscopy-Overview. *Int Res J Invent Pharm Sci*. 2013;33(3):e13370.
- [11] Gupta N, Subey A, Prasad P, Roy A. Formulation and Evaluation of Herbal Fairness Cream Comprising Hydroalcoholic Extracts of *Pleurotus ostreatus*, *Glycyrrhiza glabra* and *Camellia sinensis*. *UK J. Pharm. Biosci*. 2015;3(3):40-45.
- [12] Shah KA, Date AA, Joshi MD, Patravale VB. Solid lipid nanoparticles (SLN) of tretinoin: potential of topical delivery. *Int. J. Pharm*. 2007;345(1-2):163-71.
- [13] Marchiori ML, Lubini G, Dalla NG et al. Hydrogel containing dexamethasone loaded nanocapsules for cutaneous administration: preparation, characterization and in-vitro drug release study. *Drug development and industrial pharmacy*. 2010;36(8):962-71.
- [14] Shreedevi HM, Nesalin JAJ, Mani TT. Development and evaluation of stavudine niosomes by ether injection method. *Int J Pharm Sci Res*. 2016;7:38-46.
- [15] Saleem MN, Idris M. Formulation Design and Development of a Unani Transdermal Patch for Antiemetic Therapy and Its Pharmaceutical Evaluation. *Scientifica*. 2016;2016:1-5.
- [16] Shah V, Raval S, Peer S, Upadhyay UM. A comparative evaluation of different membranes for their diffusion efficiency: An in vitro study. *Pharma Science Monitor*. 2010;1(2):41-49.
- [17] Haigh JM, Smith EW. The selection and use of natural and synthetic membranes for in vitro diffusion experiments. *Eur. J. Pharm. Sci*. 1994;2: 311-330.